

Colorimetric Methods for the Determination of Osmium

A. K. Majumdar and J. G. Sen Gupta

JADAVPUR UNIVERSITY, CALCUTTA-32.

Osmium, a minor constituent in platinum metals, finds wide use in platinum jewellery, pen-point materials, in phonograph needles and as a catalyst. The quantity of osmium in these materials being very small, it is usually estimated colorimetrically though some workers tried with strychnine¹⁻², brucine³, 2-phenylbenzothiazole², and thionalide⁴ in its gravimetric determination.

For colorimetry, prior removal of osmium by distillation⁵⁻⁸, is preferable to do away with the influences of other platinum metals. The organic reagents proposed till now are thiourea, *NN'*-di(2-tolyl)thiourea, 1,4-diphenylthiosemicarbazide, naphthylamine sulphonic acids and tetraphenylarsonium chloride. Of these, thiourea, which forms with osmium tetroxide or chloro-osmate a rose-red colour, was first employed by Tschugaeff⁹ for detection of osmium and he found the reaction to be specific and sensitive to 0.1 p.p.m. of the element. The formula of the complex as suggested is $\text{Os}(\text{NH}_2\text{-CS-NH}_2)_6\text{-Cl}_2\text{OH}$. Sandell utilises the reagent for determination of traces of osmium, which in the tetravalent state obeys Beer's law from 1 to 3 p.p.m. Ayres and Wells¹⁰ during a spectrophotometric study of the osmium-thiourea complex observe that the system, with a sharp transmittancy minimum at 480m μ and a less applicable band centering at about 540m μ , obeys Beer's law at 480 m μ with 1 to 100 p.p.m. of osmium. The optimum concentration range is from 8 to 40 p.p.m., where the percentage relative error per 1% absolute photometric error is 2.9. Of the platinum metals, only palladium and ruthenium interfere. The thiourea method has been found suitable by Allan and Beamish¹¹ for determination of the losses of osmium by fire assay and by Dwyer and Gibson¹² for osmium in organic compounds. The suggestions of Sauerbrunn and Sandell¹³ that osmium tetroxide in its reaction with thiourea in acid medium is reduced to trivalent state to form $\text{Os}(\text{NH}_2\text{-CS-NH}_2)_3^{3+}$ is contrary to the earlier data where osmium has been claimed to be in the quadrivalent state. In another publication¹⁴ these authors suggest the removal of osmium from ruthenium by oxidation with nitric acid to tetroxide and its subsequent extraction with chloroform. The colour developed on the addition of sulphuric acid solution of thiourea to the chloroform extract is then measured at 480m μ . The method is applicable to 5 to 1000 μg . of osmium. Chloride ion should be absent because through the formation of chloro-osmate it resists the oxidation of osmium to tetroxide.

Two other reagents, *NN'*-di(2-tolyl)thiourea and 1,4-diphenylthiosemicarbazide, have been introduced by Geilmann and Neeb¹⁵ for the spectrophotometric determination

of osmium. Osmium (VI) complex formed by heating at 100° with *NN'*-di(2-tolyl)thiourea solution in 6*N* hydrochloric acid containing 5% stannous chloride is cooled and after extraction with chloroform its extinction is measured at $490\text{m}\mu$. The error is $\pm 3\%$. Oxidising agents, sulphite, palladium, rhodium and ruthenium, iridium, and platinum interfere. 1,4-Diphenylthiosemicarbazide complex of osmium is usually extracted by chloroform and measured at $520\text{m}\mu$.

With 1-naphthylamine-3,5,7-trisulphonic acid Wingfield and Yoe⁶ find the hexavalent osmium at *pH* 1.5 to form a stable violet complex having absorption maximum at $560\text{m}\mu$ and the system obeys Beer's law up to 6.0 p.p.m. The coloured constituent contains osmium and the reagent in a ratio of 1:2. A large number of ions including platinum metals interfere in the determination. The method therefore requires preliminary separation of osmium tetroxide by distillation with nitric acid. In a similar investigation of Steele and Yoe⁷ with a number of naphthylamine sulphonic acids, all the acid-osmium complexes have been found to have a fairly sharp peak at $560\text{m}\mu$ and to adhere to Beer's law over an osmate concentration of 0.1 to 6 p.p.m., but a large number of ions interfere beyond 1:1 concentration.

Tetraphenylarsonium chloride⁸ forms with a hexachloro-salt of osmium a yellow complex which is extractable by chloroform and its absorption of peak at $375\text{m}\mu$ is a suitable wave length for the study of the colour system as it obviates the interference of ions. Sulphite, perchlorate, and the ions, which are precipitated by the reagents, should be absent. Ruthenium up to 200-fold excess has no influence.

Recently Watanabe⁹ has determined osmium in presence of ruthenium by measuring the colour of sodium osmate at $520\text{m}\mu$. In this method a mixture of osmium and ruthenium is fused with sodium peroxide and sodium hydroxide and the aqueous extract is heated with ethanol at 30° to 40° for 15 minutes when ruthenium is precipitated and osmium remains in solution as sodium osmate. This is then determined in the supernatant solution.

A comparative account of these investigations is recorded in Table 1.

TABLE I

Organic colorimetric reagents for osmium.

Reagent	Oxidation-state of osmium.	Acidity or <i>pH</i> .	Analytical wave length.	Cell thickness.	Conc. range (p.p.m.)	References.
Thiourea	Octa-, tetra-	4 <i>N</i> -HCl	480 $\text{m}\mu$	1 cm.	8 to 40	6, 10-14
<i>NN'</i> -Di (2-tolyl)-thiourea	Tetra-	6 to 9 <i>N</i> HCl	490	2	15 to 175	15
1,4-Diphenylthiosemicarbazide	Do	0.05 <i>N</i>	520	2	7 to 60	15
Naphthylamine sulphonic acids	Hexa-	<i>pH</i> 1.5	560	1	1.5 to 5.5	16,17
Tetraphenylarsonium chloride	Do	0.2 to 0.3 <i>N</i> -HCl	375	2	0.3 to 1.5	18

Among the existing colorimetric methods discussed, those due to thiourea have found wide application. The unstable character of the complex and the low sensitivity of the reaction require higher concentrations of the reagent and acid. The colour reaction of naphthylamine sulphonic acid, which is believed to be due to the presence of amino group in the molecule takes long period for full colour development; it is restricted only to hexavalent osmium, which has been suggested to form a 1:2 complex with the reagent.

To examine whether the amino groups actually form a co-ordination complex with osmium and thereby develop a colour and whether organic molecules with such groups can be used as spectrophotometric reagents, systematic investigations with regard to the analytical behaviour of the aromatic amines, amino-acids, aminophenols, and aminonaphthols towards osmium, in different valence states, have been undertaken by us. These include studies on the region of maximum absorption of the colour complexes, the validity of Beer's law, optimum range with percentage relative error, the effects of *pH*, reagent, time, and foreign ions on the colour system, and the composition and dissociation constant of the complexes formed in solution. The aminophenols and aminonaphthols with suitably situated amino and hydroxyl groups behave as strong co-ordinating ligands and, moreover, these usually act as reducing agents in photography²⁰ for the reduction of gold compounds to metallic gold²¹ and of phosphomolybdate to molybdenum blue²²⁻²⁵. The amino-acids, such as anthranilic acid, are known to form inner-metallic or co-ordination complexes with a number of bivalent metals.

In what follows are given the findings on the use of anthranilic acid³¹, *m*-aminobenzoic acid³², sulphanilic acid³³, *o*-aminophenol *p*-sulphonic acid³⁴, 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid³² and 1-amino-8-naphthol-3, 6-disulphonic acid³⁴ as spectrophotometric reagents for osmium.

At the very outset it is better to point out that for studying the reaction of octavalent and tetravalent osmium with the above reagents, use has been made of pure osmium tetroxide (OsO_4) and potassium chloro-osmate (K_2OsCl_6). But since pure salt of hexavalent osmium could not be procured, it was prepared by reduction of an alkaline osmium tetroxide solution with alcohol. Reactions of osmium in different valence states with any of the reagents mentioned above lead to formation of the same complex as is evident from their identical colour reaction, same region of absorption maximum and similar tolerance to *pH* variation. But as osmium (VI) solution contains some alcohol, which causes partial bleaching of the colour, the optical density of the colour complex formed by it is always less than that of the complex formed by an equal amount of osmium (VIII) or osmium (IV). Hence the comparative data with regard to sensitivity of the reaction, adherence to Beer's law, optimum concentration range, and percentage relative error, as obtained with osmium (VIII) only, are given, though all such observations with osmium (VI) have been made.

Anthranilic acid³¹ and sulphanilic acid³³ form stable dark violet colour complexes with osmium but *m*-aminobenzoic acid³² exhibits a purple colour. These three complexes show maximum absorption at wave lengths of 460 μ , 490 μ and 500 μ and at the *pH* ranges of 5.5 to 6.5, 1.8 to 3.5, and 4.5 to 6.0 respectively. Reactions of osmium with anthranilic acid and *m*-aminobenzoic acid take place in tetra-, hexa-, and octa-valent states, but with sulphanilic acid it is restricted only to hexa- and octa-valent states. With osmium (IV) the colour develops on heating in less than 10 minutes, but with osmium (VI) and

osmium (VIII) sufficiently stable colour with maximum intensity is obtained only on keeping in the cold for an hour or two. Heating should be avoided during reactions with osmium (VI) and osmium (VIII) as otherwise black osmium dioxide separates.

With the first and the second reagents osmium (VIII) obeys Beer's law from 0.5 to 8 p.p.m., whereas for the third reagent it is from 0.5 to 9 p.p.m.; but the optimum concentration ranges, as determined by the method of Ringbom²⁶, are respectively, 2 to 6 p.p.m., 3 to 8 p.p.m., and 2 to 8 p.p.m. where the percentage relative errors per 1% absolute photometric error, evaluated by Ayres equation²⁷, are 2.8, 2.8, and 3.02.

Composition studies by the continuous variation²⁸, molar ratio²⁹, and slope ratio³⁰ methods suggest that with osmium (IV) anthranilic acid forms a 1:1 complex. The first two methods also show that a 1:2 complex is formed between osmium (VI) and sulphani-lic acid. The molar ratio method further reveals that osmium (VIII) or osmium (VI) oxidises a portion of anthranilic acid or *m*-aminobenzoic acid and is itself reduced to osmium (IV), which then reacts with the rest of the unoxidised reagent to form a 1:1 complex, the complex with the former reagent being very stable and that with the latter, unstable.

The dissociation constants of osmium (IV)-anthranilic acid and osmium (VI)-sulphanilic acid complexes are 4.6×10^{-5} and 1.2×10^{-7} respectively.

Aminophenol and aminonaphthol sulphonic acids develop a very strong coloration with octa- and hexavalent osmium in weak acid mediums, but have no action on its tetra-, tri- and bivalent states.

In both octa- and hexavalent states osmium forms in acid solutions dark brown (absorption maximum at 440 m μ) and brown (absorption maximum at 470-480 m μ) colour complexes with *o*-aminophenol-*p*-sulphonic acid, 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid and 1-amino-8-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid respectively. The optimum pH ranges are 2.5 to 4, 4 to 5.5, and 4.5 to 6.0 respectively. With *o*-aminophenol-*p*-sulphonic acid and 1-amino-8-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid Beer's law is obeyed with 1 to 10 p.p.m. of osmium (VIII) having optimum concentration range of 2 to 8 p.p.m. where percentage relative errors per 1% absolute photometric error are 2.98 and 2.93 respectively. With 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid, there is conformity to Beer's law from 1 to 14 p.p.m. of osmium with an optimum range of 3 to 10 p.p.m. The percentage relative error per 1% absolute photometric error for the said range is 2.82.

Composition studies of the three complexes in acid solutions indicate that osmium (VI) forms a 1:2 complex with each of these reagents. The dissociation constants of dark brown, brown, and brownish black complexes are 1.2×10^{-7} , 2.05×10^{-9} , and 1.2×10^{-9} respectively.

Application of the molar ratio method to the dark brown and brownish black complexes points to the fact that the reagent is first oxidised by osmium (VIII) and then the excess of the reagent forms a 1:2 complex with the reduced osmium (VI).

A comparative account of the reactions is shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Reagent.	Oxidation state of osmium.	pH.	Wave length for max. absorption.	Conc. range of osmium for adherence to Beer's law (p.p.m.).	Sensitivity (μcm^2)	Complex nature (Metal: reagent ratio).	Dissociation constant of the complex.
Anthranilic acid	Octa-, hexa- and tetra-	5.5 to 6.5	460 m μ	0.5 to 8 for Os (IV) or Os (VIII)	0.008 for Os (IV) or Os (VIII)	1 : 1 between Os (IV) and reagent	4.6×10^{-5}
<i>m</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	Do	4.5 to 6.0	500	0.5 to 8 for Os (VIII)	0.012 for Os(VIII)	Probably 1:1 between Os (IV) and reagent	..
Sulphanilic acid	Octa- and hexa-	1.8 to 3.5	490	0.5 to 9 for Os (VIII)	0.01 for Os (VIII)	1:2 between Os (VI) and reagent	1.2×10^{-7}
<i>o</i> -Aminophenol- β -sulphonic acid	Do	2.5 to 4.0	440	1 to 10 for Os (VIII)	0.01 for Os (VIII)	1:2 between Os (VI) and reagent	1.2×10^{-7}
1-Amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid	Do	4.0 to 5.5	470-480	1 to 14 for Os (VIII)	0.014 for Os(VIII)	1:2 between Os(VI) and reagent	2.05×10^{-9}
1-Amino-8-naphthol-3, 6-disulphonic acid	Do	4.5 to 6.0	480	1 to 10 for Os (VIII)	0.011 for Os(VIII)	1:2 between Os(VI) and reagent	1.2×10^{-9}

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